

ISic1114

I.Sicily inscription 1114

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

(?)

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)**Place of origin (modern)**

Alcamo

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Alcamo

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140597

1. [— —]IEPAI [— —]
2. [— —]KΩNOΣ [— —]
3. [— —]ΘEATPOY [— —]
- 4.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492730

EDCS 39102271

PHI 140597

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. *Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. Inscriptiones Graecae consilio*

et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV. Berlin.
At 14.0293 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)
Boeckh, A., Franz, J., Curtius, E., Kirchhoff, A., Roehl, H. 1828-1887. *Corpus
Inscriptionum Graecarum*. Berlin. At 3.5550

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